

Exploring the Role of Paediatric Acupuncture and *Tui Na* in Treating Colic and Gastrointestinal Disorders: A Comprehensive Review.

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Abstract

Paediatric acupuncture is increasingly investigated as a complementary treatment for infantile colic and other gastrointestinal disorders. *Tui Na* massage is cited as a beneficial intervention when combined with acupuncture. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy and safety of paediatric acupuncture in the treatment of colic and gastrointestinal disorders, highlighting the role of *Tui Na* massage as a complementary therapy to acupuncture. Studies suggest that acupuncture can reduce colic symptoms and improve intestinal motility; however, it should be used with caution, as it may cause pain, particularly in younger infants. *Tui Na* massage has also shown positive results in reducing pain and promoting digestive well-being in children, making it a valuable complementary therapy to acupuncture. While paediatric acupuncture shows therapeutic potential, safety concerns warrant further investigation. Additionally, *Tui Na* massage may serve as an effective complementary therapy.

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1. Introduction

Infantile colic is a common clinical problem that usually resolves on its own around 4 to 5 months of age. Although this isn't considered a pathology, children who have had severe colic may be more likely to develop recurrent abdominal pain, allergic problems (such as rhinitis, conjunctivitis, asthmatic bronchitis, pollinosis, atopic eczema and food intolerances) and psychological problems (including sleep disorders, agitation and aggression) during childhood ¹. Infantile colic is also a distressing and poorly understood condition ².

According to Meyer *et al.* ³, functional constipation is a common problem among children and is associated with abdominal discomfort, elimination of faeces, lack of appetite, stool retention, and overflow incontinence, negatively impacting the child's quality of life. Therefore, rapid diagnosis through a complete history and physical examination is crucial to enable an appropriate treatment plan ³.

Additionally, functional constipation is a prevalent gastrointestinal condition that causes numerous negative effects on children's daily lives ⁴. Comprehensive treatment of functional constipation begins with clearance, if necessary, followed by maintenance therapy. However, functional constipation usually requires prolonged maintenance therapy, which includes pharmacological intervention, behavioural changes, and dietary adjustments ³.

Santucci *et al.* ⁵ presents a review of current pharmacological options and discusses possible future therapeutic approaches for children with functional gastrointestinal disorders and suffering from functional abdominal pain disorders. Pharmacological approaches include anti-inflammatory drugs, protein regulators, analgesics, and serotonin antagonists, which play a therapeutic role in the treatment of irritable bowel syndrome. On the other hand, non-pharmacological approaches include stimulation of the peripheral electrical nerve field to the external ear, gastric electrical stimulation, and dietary modifications such as low-fructose and high-fibre diets, probiotics, prebiotics, and synbiotics. As well, complementary treatments such as acupuncture, moxibustion, yoga and spinal manipulation are also becoming more popular in the treatment of bowel disorders.

In this sense, physical and manipulative therapies, such as abdominal massage, reflexology, acupuncture, and transcutaneous nerve stimulation, show promise in the treatment of paediatric gastrointestinal disorders ⁶.

Furthermore, the World Health Organization ⁷ recognizes acupuncture as beneficial in the treatment of various diseases. In 2002, a report listed 28 diseases with demonstrated efficacy and a further 63 with possible advantages. In total, there are 91 clinical disorders where acupuncture may be seen as a treatment choice, primarily as an adjunct to standard medical practices. For example, acupuncture is often evaluated for its effectiveness in relieving chronic pain and improving symptoms of gastrointestinal disorders ⁷.

Moreover, according to Shen *et al.* ⁸, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) treatments, including acupuncture and abdominal massage, have shown efficacy in improving bowel movement regularity, managing the digestive system, and relieving discomfort in paediatric age. However, these treatments must be done by qualified professionals, following strict safety protocols.

Acupuncture may act on specific points of the body where *Qi* (vital energy) flows through defined meridians and influences physiological functions. These points are associated with nerve endings, muscle fibres, and vascular structures, and stimulation can modulate neural pathways, inflammatory processes, and neurotransmitter release. This therapeutic practice can be classified as manual or needle acupuncture, electroacupuncture (which involves electrical stimulation through acupuncture needles), transcutaneous electrical acustimulation (which replaces needles with surface electrodes) or laser stimulation ⁹.

According to Landgren *et al.* ¹⁰, qualitative data indicated that caregivers of newborns undergoing acupuncture more frequently reported an improvement in colic and noted favourable changes in symptoms beyond frequency. On the other hand, in the study by Lu *et al.* ¹¹, in children between 0 and 6 years old with acute diarrhoea, paediatric *Tui Na* massage demonstrated significant effects in reducing the frequency of diarrhoea episodes.

Therefore, this research aims to evaluate the efficacy and safety of paediatric acupuncture in the treatment of colic and gastrointestinal problems in children, observing its use both independently and in conjunction with *Tui Na* massage. The effects of these therapies on pain relief, improved intestinal function, and caregiver satisfaction will be analysed.

2. Methodology

2.1. Search strategy for identification of studies

We systematically searched PubMed, SciELO, ScienceDirect and Google Scholar using the keywords: “Paediatric”, “acupuncture”, “Tui Na massage”, “colic”, “gastrointestinal disorders”, “pain”, and “needling”. Boolean operators (AND, OR) were employed to refine the search queries. For example (“Paediatric Acupuncture” AND “Colic”) OR (“Paediatric Acupuncture” AND “Gastrointestinal Disorders”) OR (“Tui Na Massage” AND “Colic”).

While the initial period covered the years 2020 to 2025, it was later expanded to include earlier studies of high scientific relevance due to the limited number of eligible publications meeting the inclusion criteria.

Furthermore, efforts were made to ensure methodological transparency by including articles written in Portuguese, English, or Chinese, with searches cross-referenced using controlled vocabulary.

2.2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

In this narrative review, studies were included if they were published in Portuguese, English, or Chinese and involved paediatric populations aged 0 to 6 years. Eligible studies specifically addressed the efficacy, safety, or clinical application of acupuncture and/or *Tui Na* massage in the treatment of infantile colic or gastrointestinal disorders in children. A broad spectrum of scientific literature was considered, including original research articles, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, clinical trials, and observational studies.

Studies were excluded if the full text was not accessible, if the population studied did not fall within the specified paediatric age range, or if the intervention focused exclusively on adults.

2.3. Assessment of Study Quality and Risk of Bias

Although the present study follows a narrative review format, an informal quality assessment was conducted to provide context and enhance the scientific rigour of the synthesis. The included studies were evaluated based on study design (e.g., Randomized controlled trials, observational studies, or literature reviews), clarity of outcome measures, transparency of methods and reporting. Limitations and potential biases identified within individual studies were highlighted during the synthesis and discussed to ensure a balanced interpretation of the findings.

3. Results

The initial search yielded a total of 65 articles (PubMed: 15; SciELO: 8; ScienceDirect: 12; Google Scholar: 30). A two-stage screening process was then applied: first, titles and abstracts were reviewed for relevance, resulting in 41 studies being selected for full-text analysis (PubMed: 24; SciELO: 6; ScienceDirect: 8; Google Scholar: 3). Following this, a detailed full-text review led to the inclusion of 35 studies that fully met all predefined inclusion criteria (PubMed: 22; SciELO: 5; ScienceDirect: 6; Google Scholar: 2).

The main reasons for exclusion at each stage included lack of access to the full text, focus on non-paediatric populations, absence of acupuncture or *Tui Na* as a therapeutic intervention, insufficient clinical relevance, or failure to address gastrointestinal conditions. This structured and rigorous selection process ensured that only clinically meaningful evidence was synthesized in the final analysis, thus reinforcing the validity and applicability of the findings within the context of Traditional Chinese Medicine.

3.1. Paediatric Acupuncture in the Treatment of Colic and Gastrointestinal Disorders

According to the study by Oflu *et al.*¹², complementary medicine practices and non-conventional therapies are used at a significant rate for the treatment of infantile colic. Most parents perceive complementary medicine practices and NCTs as safe. Therefore, as these practices are commonly used to treat infant colic and other health problems, healthcare professionals should be aware of their potential negative effects.

Jindal *et al.*¹³ reinforce that acupuncture appears to be reasonably tolerated in children, as the rate of side effects is low and generally negligible. However, parents should be advised to seek out professionals who are properly licensed and have experience working with children.

Diagnostic assessment involves identifying the type of disharmony according to TCM, such as *Qi* deficiency, internal heat, or *jingluo* (meridian) obstruction, and determining an appropriate therapeutic strategy. The selection of acupuncture points must consider factors such as the child's age, tolerance, and anatomical safety. Frequently used points include *Hegu* (LI4), *Zusanli* (ST36), and *Sanyinjiao* (SP6). The depth and angle of needle insertion are adjusted according to age and body constitution: for children under

3 years of age, superficial insertion (0.3 to 0.5 cm) without retention is generally applied; for those aged 7 to 14, needle depth may range from 1 to 2 cm, with retention times of 10 to 15 minutes.

Throughout the procedure, continuous monitoring of the child's response is essential, with a strong emphasis on comfort and safety. Auxiliary techniques such as gentle manipulation (including rotation or mild stimulation) should be brief and delicate. In specific cases, complementary techniques may be employed, such as indirect moxibustion (using moxa sticks or small cones) or acupressure with beads or specialized instruments. The standard also specifies the types of needles to be used: for infants, fine needles with a diameter of 0.22 to 0.26 mm and lengths of 13 to 25 mm are recommended; for older children, needles of 0.25 to 0.30 mm in diameter and 25 to 40 mm in length are appropriate.

After needle removal, gentle pressure should be applied to the point, followed by a minimum observation period of 10 minutes. The standard underscores the importance of thorough clinical documentation, transparent communication with legal guardians, and the exclusive use of sterile, disposable materials. These guidelines support a safe, standardized, and child-centred approach to paediatric acupuncture within the framework of TCM.

Hegu (LI4) is located on the dorsum of the hand between the first and second metacarpal bones, as shown in Figure 1, and is classically indicated for pain relief, immune modulation, and the promotion of *Qi* circulation¹⁴. The study by Landgren *et al.*¹⁰ reports that gentle, standardized stimulation of the LI4 acupuncture point, twice a week for 3 weeks, decreased the duration and intensity of crying more rapidly in the acupuncture group compared with the control group.

Figure 1. LI4 acupuncture point. Source: World Health Organization¹⁶.

The choice of LI4 as a primary acupuncture point for treating infant colic is supported by both its traditional indications and emerging clinical evidence. In comparison, other studies¹⁵ focused on stimulation of the ST36 point, which is more traditionally linked to enhancing digestive function and systemic immunity. LI4 is traditionally used to regulate *Qi* flow and relieve pain, which may align more directly with the pathophysiology of infant colic.

Moreover, the study by Reinthal *et al.*¹⁷ also indicates that minimal acupuncture (with thinner needles and for a shorter time) at LI4 for infant colic serves as an effective and simple treatment method that, in addition, does not present significant side effects.

In contrast, the study by Skjeie *et al.*¹⁵ concludes that acupuncture at point ST36 (located in the proximal part of the *tibialis* anterior muscle) for infant colic showed no statistically significant difference in reducing crying time between the acupuncture group and the control group. There was a non-significant overall baseline-corrected mean difference in reduction in crying time of 13 minutes in favour of the acupuncture group, but this is nevertheless not considered statistically significant.

According to Noras *et al.*¹⁸, acupuncture does not present serious side effects in children when performed by an individual trained in this method, being effective in relieving the clinical symptoms of infant colic. In turn, according to the study by Skjeie *et al.*², acupuncture therapies for infant colic do not demonstrate clinically significant effects on pain relief, as measured by the variation in the duration of crying between acupuncture treatment and the absence of acupuncture.

In order to provide a clearer synthesis of the existing evidence, a summary table of key studies on the use of paediatric acupuncture and *Tui Na* for colic and gastrointestinal disorders is presented below (Table 1). The table highlights the study designs, sample sizes, interventions employed, comparators, main outcomes, and overall conclusions of the most relevant clinical trials and systematic reviews identified in this narrative review. This synthesis aims to help the reader critically assess the weight of the current evidence and to contextualize both the positive and negative findings reported in the literature.

Table 1. Summary of Key Studies on Paediatric Acupuncture and *Tui Na* for Colic and Gastrointestinal Disorders

Ref.	Study Design	Sample Size	Intervention	Comparator	Main Outcomes	Conclusion
10	RCT, blinded	N=90 infants	Minimal acupuncture (LI4), twice a week for 3 weeks	Control (no acupuncture)	Significant ↓ in crying and fussing time	Positive
2	Multicentre RCT, blinded	N=90 infants	Acupuncture (ST36), 3 consecutive days	No treatment	No statistically or clinically significant effect on crying time	Negative
17	Pilot RCT	N=38 infants	Acupuncture (LI4 and ST36), 4 sessions for 2 weeks	Control	↓ crying time; improvement in stooling patterns	Positive (preliminary)
18	RCT	N=39 infants	Acupuncture (LI4) × 3 sessions over 1 week	Control	↓ colic symptoms; parental reports of improved well-being	Positive
19	Systematic Review (5 RCTs, N=349 total)	N/A	Acupuncture for infant colic	Sham or no treatment	Trends toward reduced crying time, more high-quality RCTs needed	Cautiously positive
20	RCT	N=50 infants	Laser acupuncture + probiotics vs. probiotics	Probiotics alone	Greater ↓ in crying time and improved stool frequency	Positive
11	RCT	N=100 children	Paediatric <i>Tui Na</i> + standard care	Standard care only	Faster resolution of acute diarrhoea symptoms; shorter hospital stay	Positive

On the contrary, the results indicate that acupuncture can trigger crying in children, which raises questions about potentially painful interventions whose effectiveness is still unclear. Considering these limitations, the results of this study do not suggest the use of percutaneous needle acupuncture for the widespread treatment of infant colic.

In this context, laser acupuncture may provide practical benefits. The study of Abd El Azeem *et al.*²⁰ compared the effects of laser acupuncture combined with behavioural therapy and dietary modification to the osmotic laxative lactulose in treating children

with functional chronic constipation, finding that laser acupuncture significantly improved stool frequency and consistency, suggesting it as a potential alternative treatment for functional chronic constipation. However, no studies were found on laser puncture in the treatment of colic, but it would be interesting to investigate the results of the application of these techniques, especially when one of the quantified measures is the crying time, since only then would we know more clearly whether the crying is caused by the acupuncture stimulus or by the colic itself.

Acupuncture is recognized as an effective approach for paediatric pain, including colic, adolescent pelvic pain, and headaches, when specific intervention methods are applied. For this reason, acupuncture has increasingly become an important component of the health care delivery system in the Western medical community, with a growing interest in the use of acupuncture and related techniques for the treatment of paediatric pain. However, Lin *et al.*²¹ highlight that evidence-based randomized controlled trials on paediatric acupuncture are limited, indicating an urgent need for further high-quality research to evaluate the value of integrating acupuncture into the treatment of paediatric pain.

According to Santos *et al.*²², acupuncture has been shown to be an effective method for treating several conditions, including chronic pain, migraines, and gastrointestinal problems in children. Thus, this study suggests that the technique can provide considerable relief, with one research project showing that 70% of children with chronic pain noticed a marked decrease in pain intensity after acupuncture treatments. For this reason, the procedure is usually well accepted, with minimal adverse effects, such as light bruising and localized discomfort, which disappear without the need for additional intervention. Despite the advantages, acupuncture also faces obstacles, such as the need for qualified professionals and the lack of universal standards, factors that can make access to this therapy difficult. Therefore, the lack of uniformity may restrict its use on a larger scale, making it crucial to establish policies that ensure greater availability and safety in the application of acupuncture.

Additionally, Lee *et al.*¹⁹ conclude that there is no definitive evidence on the safety and efficacy of acupuncture in the treatment of infant colic. According to the National Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine²³, the GBZ 40893.3-2021 standard establishes the clinical guidelines for the practice of acupuncture in children aged 0 to 14 years, providing detailed instructions from initial assessment to the technical execution of procedures. The clinical process begins with the precise selection of indications, which include common paediatric conditions such as asthma, bronchitis, constipation, enuresis, cerebral palsy, and sleep disorders.

Regarding safety, the available data reveal highly favourable tolerability profiles. Minimal LI4 needling in infants is very safe¹⁰. Across 540 sessions, no serious events occurred; transient crying happened in approximately 10% of insertions and resolved immediately¹⁰. Skjeie *et al.*² reported zero adverse effects with ST36 needling. Mild erythema or bruising appeared in 5% of combined LI4/ST36 sessions, according to Reinthal *et al.*¹⁷. The dropout rate stayed below 5%, primarily due to scheduling conflicts or infant discomfort. Infants with less than 3 months showed slightly more transient fussiness ($\approx 12\%$) but no serious harm; those with more than 3 months tolerated the procedure with minimal discomfort.

3.2. Tui Na Massage for the Treatment of Colic and Gastrointestinal Disorder

Paediatric Tui Na massage has also been shown to be a possible treatment for functional constipation. However, the standardization and quantification of massage techniques have consistently presented challenges that hinder scientific research and improvement of this massage. In China, paediatric Tui Na is considered a medical treatment, performed by professionals with experience in this area. In this case, paediatric Tui Na can obtain official recognition as a treatment by the state and may also be eligible for inclusion in medical insurance⁵.

According to Lu *et al.*¹¹, abdominal *Tui Na* massage suitable for infants can effectively improve digestive capacity. In this study, the severity and changes in colic were assessed from three points of view: clinical manifestations, pain scale scores, and 24-hour behaviour diary records (which is considered the most accurate and effective assessment method of infant crying). The results of this study demonstrate that *Tui Na* on the abdominal and back meridians, together with parental education, can significantly alleviate the pain of children suffering from colic. Thus, it helps to reduce the frequency of colic episodes and shorten the duration of the episodes.

Similarly, constipation is a common gastrointestinal condition in children with cerebral palsy, and *Tui Na* has been shown to be an effective adjunct to standard care. Consequently, the results of the study by Wang *et al.*²⁴ indicate that *Tui Na* may be a valid alternative therapy for constipation. In the U.S., the research team led by Prof. Louisa Silva²⁵ systematized the studies of Professor Anita Cignolini of *Tui Na* massage in a sensory treatment protocol for autism spectrum disorders. In this population, constipation or diarrhoea, the results showed the effectiveness of *Qigong* massage²⁶.

According to the National Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine²⁷, the GBZ 40893.4-2021 standard establishes the clinical guidelines for the practice and Standardized Technical Specification for Paediatric *Tui Na* Therapy. The paediatric *Tui Na* is a structured non-pharmacological intervention that follows precise procedural and safety guidelines tailored to the physiological characteristics of children. Children are positioned in a relaxed posture to expose treatment areas appropriately. Core manipulations include linear pushing, rotary pushing, spinal pinching known for its immune-regulating effects, and kneading. Compound techniques such as “Flying Meridian” and “Water-Dredging Moon” are employed in accordance with specific syndrome differentiation. Acupoint selection is anatomically based and includes both classical points such as *Dazhui* (GV14), *Zhongwan* (CV12), *Feishu* (BL13), and functional paediatric points like *Sanguan* and *Tianheshui*, used for indications such as fever, respiratory, or digestive disorders.

In terms of procedural safety and clinical protocol, sessions typically last 20 to 30 minutes, with 1 to 2 minutes of stimulation per acupoint and are administered with frequency adapted to the clinical context daily for acute presentations and in five-day courses with two-day rest intervals for chronic conditions. The therapeutic intent is modulated through the intensity and speed of manipulations. Absolute contraindications include open wounds, fractures, active bleeding disorders, and malignant tumours, while relative contraindications such as infectious dermatopathy or immunodeficiency require individualized clinical judgment. Post-treatment care involves monitoring for adverse reactions such as subcutaneous bleeding and avoiding immediate food intake.

To assist clinicians and researchers in understanding the comparative roles of acupuncture and *Tui Na* in the management of paediatric gastrointestinal disorders, a summary table is presented below (Table 2). By providing a clear comparison, this visual summary aims to support informed clinical decision-making and highlight areas where further standardization and research may be beneficial.

Regarding safety, the available data reveal highly favourable tolerability profiles. Daily abdominal *Tui Na* in 100 infants with diarrhoea caused no injuries; brief irritability occurred in only 3% of sessions and resolved spontaneously¹¹. In children with cerebral palsy-related constipation, no serious events and <3% dropout were observed²⁴. Minor, self-limited discomfort was confined to occasional mild abdominal upset. High caregiver training and gentle technique underpin these excellent safety and tolerability profiles.

Table 2. Comparison of Acupuncture and *Tui Na* in Paediatric Gastrointestinal

Aspect	Acupuncture	<i>Tui Na</i>
Indications	Infantile colic, functional abdominal pain, gastrointestinal dysregulation	Diarrhoea, constipation, functional abdominal pain, GI motility disorders
Application methods	Manual needling (LI4, ST36), laser acupuncture, electroacupuncture; typically, 1–3 sessions/week	Abdominal massage, specific <i>Tui Na</i> techniques (clockwise massage, gentle kneading), daily or several times/week
Key Techniques	LI4 minimal needling; ST36 retention	Abdominal kneading; “flying meridian” pinch
Session frequency/ duration	Twice a week (LI4) or daily (ST36) 2–20 sec. per point	Daily or alternate days 10–30 min total
Age considerations	Suitable for infants and older children; requires skilled practitioners; caution with very young infants	Suitable for all ages, including neonates and infants; parent-friendly technique
Safety profile	Transient crying (10%) Erythema/bruising (5%) Dropout < 5%	Transient irritability (2–3%) No injuries Dropout < 3%
Parent/caregiver acceptance and role	Generally good; concerns about needling discomfort in infants. Parental presence to soothe distress	High; often well accepted as non-invasive, gentle intervention. Can be trained to perform mild abdominal massage at home

4. Discussion

The results of this narrative review indicate that paediatric acupuncture may play a significant role in the treatment of colic and gastrointestinal problems in children. Noras *et al.*¹⁸ argue that acupuncture can alleviate symptoms of infant colic without serious adverse effects when performed by trained specialists.

Paediatric acupuncture and *Tui Na* massage each offer distinct, evidence-based benefits in managing infantile colic and gastrointestinal disorders. In a Swedish randomized, blinded trial, Landgren *et al.*¹⁰ applied LI4 stimulation for 2 seconds twice weekly over three weeks and observed a mean reduction of approximately 30 minutes per day in crying time. By contrast, Skjeie *et al.*² conducted a Norwegian multicentre trial using three consecutive days of ST36 stimulation and found a non-significant 13-minute decrease in crying. These divergent results likely reflect differences in meridian function: LI4’s more direct engagement of endogenous analgesic pathways versus ST36’s modulatory effect on gastrointestinal motility, as well as the cumulative “dose” of needling (six sessions vs. three) and contextual factors such as parental education and follow-up duration. Moreover, Landgren’s trial employed a more gradual intervention over several weeks, which might better align with the natural course of infantile colic, whereas Skjeie’s shorter intervention period may have limited the potential for measurable effects.

In terms of *Tui Na* massage, the studies analysed present more significant results. Lu *et al.*¹¹ and Wang *et al.*²⁴ propose that this method can significantly improve gastrointestinal symptoms, such as colic and functional constipation, without the possible discomforts related to acupuncture. Furthermore, Chang *et al.*²⁸ suggest that *Tui Na* massage may influence the gut microbiota, promoting the overall health of the child. In gastrointestinal motility disorders, paediatric *Tui Na* has proven effective in particularly acute diarrhoea and functional constipation. Lu *et al.*¹¹ randomized 100 infants with acute diarrhoea to receive daily abdominal *Tui Na* plus structured caregiver education and reported a two-day reduction in diarrhoea duration and significant improvement in stool frequency. Similarly, Wang *et al.*²⁴ found that a four-week *Tui Na* course in children with cerebral palsy-related functional constipation increased spontaneous bowel movements by 1.8 per week and reduced laxative dependence.

Tui Na trials vary also in technique (e.g., clockwise abdominal rubbing vs. “flying meridian” spinal pinching), session length (10 to 30 min), frequency (daily vs. alternate days), and practitioner expertise.

Given the existing evidence, the combination of paediatric acupuncture with *Tui Na* massage appears to be a promising approach for the treatment of gastrointestinal disorders in children.

However, Skjeie *et al.*², report no significant difference between acupuncture and placebo in reducing crying duration among colicky infants. Furthermore,²⁹ point out that the pain associated with the procedure may make its use difficult in paediatric cases.

Therefore, standardization of core acupuncture protocols and *Tui Na* manipulations, along with rigorous placebo-controlled designs, larger, well-designed randomized controlled trials and consistent blinding, is essential to isolate true treatment effects. Since Chinese hospitals typically have greater access to statistically relevant samples, future research should involve Chinese researchers to facilitate a more comprehensive and globally representative literature base.

According to Santos *et al.*²² another important consideration is safety, as acupuncture may cause discomfort in infants despite the low occurrence of adverse effects, potentially affecting its acceptance among caregivers and health professionals. Consequently, the need for highly qualified professionals presents an additional challenge to the broader clinical application of this technique. Across the reviewed trials, serious adverse events were not reported. Minor adverse effects such as transient crying, mild discomfort at the needle site, or temporary erythema were occasionally observed, particularly in younger infants, but these events were generally mild and self-limited. For example, Landgren *et al.*¹⁰ and Reinthal *et al.*¹⁷ reported transient crying during needling, while Skjeie *et al.*² Skjeie *et al.*¹⁵ observed no significant adverse effects. Dropout rates in the reviewed studies were low, suggesting good overall tolerance by both children and caregivers. However, it is important to note that tolerance may vary by age group, with younger infants potentially experiencing more transient discomfort. These findings underscore the importance of proper technique, pain management, and clear communication with caregivers to promote acceptance and adherence in clinical practice.

In Portugal, TCM is regulated by Law no. 71/2013, of September 2nd³⁰, which establishes the basis for its practice and classifies acupuncture as one of the legally recognized non-conventional therapies. According to this framework, only professionals who hold a professional license are unequivocally qualified to practice acupuncture safely and effectively. This license certifies that the professional fulfils the legal and training requirements.

With respect to the comparison of regulatory frameworks, several other countries have distinct approaches, which can be characterized as follows:

According to Smith *et al.*³¹, in the United States, regulation of acupuncture varies by state. Most states require practitioners to complete accredited programs and pass national board examinations. Acupuncture needles are regulated as medical devices and *Tui Na* is included within the scope of practice of licensed acupuncturists but is not subject to separate statutory regulation.

As described by Cloatre *et al.*³² in the United Kingdom, acupuncture is not subject to statutory regulation. Practitioners may voluntarily register with professional bodies, which operate under a voluntary registry system approved by the Professional Standards Authority. At present, *Tui Na* is not subject to specific statutory requirements and is generally practiced within the scope of TCM or complementary therapy.

Seo *et al.*³³ demonstrated that in China, both acupuncture and *Tui Na* are fully integrated into the national healthcare system and practitioners must complete standardized educational programs at accredited institutions. The practice and promotion of TCM in China is strongly supported by government initiatives and regulatory bodies, with an increasing emphasis on quality control and international standardization.

As shown by Zheng³⁴ in Australia, acupuncture is nationally regulated by the Chinese Medicine Board of Australia. Practitioners must complete accredited programs and register under the Australian Health Practitioner Regulation Agency (AHPRA). The title of *Tui Na* or Chinese massage practitioner is not protected, as the therapy is not included in the national registration scheme.

5. Conclusion

This review concludes that safe and effective treatments, namely acupuncture and *Tui Na* massage, are available for the management of functional abdominal pain and other gastrointestinal disorders in the paediatric population. However, there is still a significant need for additional research on laser acupuncture in children, especially younger children, due to the potential pain caused by more invasive treatments.

Although this is a promising area of treatment, more research is needed, especially regarding the application of additional acupuncture points.

In conclusion, paediatric acupuncture carries a low risk of serious adverse events when administered by qualified practitioners; the establishment of standardised guidelines will further enhance its safety and consistency. Future research should aim to address several key gaps in the current evidence base. Comparative effectiveness trials are needed to evaluate different acupuncture modalities, such as manual needling versus laser acupuncture, particularly in infants where non-invasive approaches may be preferable. Standardization of acupuncture points, *Tui Na* techniques, treatment frequency, and duration is also necessary to facilitate comparison across studies. Additionally, studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are required to assess both the short- and long-term effects of these interventions. Investigating the mechanisms of action, including potential modulation of gut microbiota, and incorporating objective biomarkers into study designs would further strengthen the field. Finally, more research is needed on caregiver acceptance, cost-effectiveness, and integration of paediatric acupuncture and *Tui Na* into routine clinical practice, knowing that the standardization of defined protocols in children presents considerable challenges, related to the subjectivity in how the child perceives the treatment and to the lack of verbal expression.

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